

DEVELOPMENT OF THE COGNITIVE COMPETENCE OF THE STUDENTS OF UNIVERSAL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

Madinakhon Alimova Iskandar kizi

“TIAME” NRU researcheradmin

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8377276>

Abstract. *This article focuses on the issues of forming the cognitive competence of students of general education institutions in English using innovative technologies, and the importance of cognitive psychology.*

Keywords: *learner, english, english language teaching, cognitive competence, linguistic personality.*

The modern social and cultural environment is characterized by the large-scale development of multilingualism, and the acquisition of languages, including foreign languages, is becoming the most important issue in the formation of a linguistic personality. According to the famous scientist A.N. Shchukin, "mastering a language means mastering language units (linguistic material), as well as the rules and methods of using language units in the process of communication.»

It is worth noting that the positive influence of the state on the subject of the education of the young generation and the support of all-round labor activities on the subject of legislation is being strengthened in regulatory documents. In these documents, great attention is paid to the quality of education and upbringing of the young generation, as well as the compatibility of the local level of education. Aloha attention was also paid to the issue of taking into account modern world standards and norms.

The search for innovative ways to increase the quality of education is related to the modern market relations, which have increasingly complicated the requirements for the content of education, the methods of organizing the educational process. challenges the knowledge paradigm of education, prompting a reorientation of the entire education system in line with a competency-based approach to education.

Currently, the education of our country is being adapted to innovative technological processes. There is a normal process of creating a communication and information environment faced by high school students of the republic's general education institutions. Issues related to activation of cognitive-mental activity in learning a foreign (English) language, using modern technology and equipment, entering the field of intercultural communication, independently receiving and processing information from various sources, are not left out of the authorities' attention. of course.

A graduate of a general education institution is required to acquire solid language skills through the means of a foreign (English) language, to develop foreign language skills and competencies that help to actively participate in social and cultural relations, as well as to actively participate in studies. cried These include various meetings, events, Olympiads, conferences, etc. It can be seen that the individual psychological qualities and characteristics of students and the

level of preparation for a foreign language, their independent organization, cognitive and mental potential and the ability to use it in the practice of communication in a foreign language are the most important components of formation.

The modern education system does not provide a high-quality level of comprehensive abilities in high school students of general educational institutions, despite the requirements of the era about the need to form a language personality focused on the existence of universal linguistic and communicative capabilities. This situation justifies the relevance of the use of modern technologies in the field of education, aimed at training a linguistic person among school graduates in the conditions of a continuous flow of input data. Such a setting should have a cognitive pedagogy that allows:

preparing students of general education institutions for the strict requirements of modern society, including in the context of teaching and learning English;

connecting the organization of the process of learning a foreign language not with the implementation of its communicative tasks, but with social expediency and predetermined standards arising from the established socio-cultural conditions and perspectives of the young generation.

Based on the requirements of today's time, English language teaching in general educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan starts from the 1st grade. Activities of the youngest representatives of the younger generation with materials in a foreign language are very important and priority during the entire period of study. Taking into account all its levels (phonetics, vocabulary, grammar) of the subject "English language" based on the normative standard, the use of innovative technologies helps young students acquire the necessary knowledge of the English language. This will serve as a foundation for schoolchildren to continue their studies in higher educational institutions in the future.

It is known that world languages are not only the main means of human communication, but also an important cognitive-mental tool. From this point of view, learning English in the general educational institutions of our country represents the formation of two most important qualities in teaching subjects - understanding and speech (perception/reproduction). These priority components of speech activity (including reading and writing) are the main signs in the development of a linguistic personality. In fact, mastering these components of speech activity provides the process of forming the cognitive-mental competence of students studying in general education institutions of our country in teaching English. In other words, it is a direct way to develop students' cognitive-mental competence and provides a normal course of effective communication in foreign language communication.

From this point of view, the formation of the cognitive-mental competence of students in the upper classes of general education institutions in the English language, learning the language with the help of information and communication technologies is of particular practical importance.

The problems of effective organization of the educational process in the context of the requirements for increasing the cognitive and mental activity of students in educational institutions have been developed in the science of local pedagogy. Various aspects of formation of educational and cognitive activities of educational subjects, development of thinking abilities were the object of special attention of scientists and teachers of our country.

The problem of developing the cognitive competence of high school students in English is urgent, because in the conditions of modern reality, a large-scale multicultural and multilingual

panorama opens before the language person, which contributes to the successful career and professional growth of the young generation.

In the process of teaching English in general education schools, it is recommended to consider the effective model of the development of students' cognitive activity from the point of view of the category of "teaching cognitive-mental activity", it is also appropriate to consider it as an integrative component based on the following factors:

cognitive-mental activity understood as the development of logical thinking of high school students in English;

restructuring of the educational process in accordance with the goals and objectives of the foreign language;

to consider high school students as active subjects of English language teaching;

to ensure constructive cooperation and mutual cooperation in the teacher-student format" ("partnership" principle).

It should also be noted that the development of students' cognitive activity in English language teaching should be carried out in the context of changes, including the revision of the content and components of "cognitive-mental teaching" and "cognitive activity". , based on the criteria of its formation, it is also permissible to introduce methodological support and improvement works.

The problem of developing cognitive abilities of older students is relevant for English language classes, because in the conditions of modern reality, a large-scale multicultural and multilingual panorama opens before the linguist, which contributes to the successful career and professional growth of the younger generation.

Formation of the cognitive competence of high school students in the English language is one of the important and multifaceted problems of the science of psychology and pedagogy. This is consistent with the principles of student-centered and developmental education as the main catalyst for the success of teaching English as a foreign language in the modern environment of the development of multilingualism and multiculturalism.

From this point of view, it is necessary to consider the main paradigms of foreign language education in the context of the requirements for modern pedagogy.

Here, the concept of "Paradigm" should be considered by the researcher with the positions of the theoretical and methodological aspects of the "standard" studied issues, solving the actual practical problems of cognitive activation, mental activity of high school students in learning English.

The cognitive paradigm in the pedagogical aspect is characterized by a number of features derived from the concept of "cognitive" (Latin cogito - thinking) and refers to the process of cognitive thinking. Teaching English is accompanied by the acquisition of knowledge, development of skills and abilities that help to activate the cognitive and thinking abilities of students. The main source of knowledge is the teacher and textbooks. In this, the student appears as an object of learning, and here his main goal is to acquire knowledge, skills and competences. The student's personality-oriented qualities are manifested only if he shows initiative and self-organization under conditions of increased cognitive motivation. In other words, teaching English in the upper classes of general education institutions is the practical implementation of theoretical knowledge by analyzing, summarizing and analyzing the language material during and after the lesson.

It is known that the cognitive direction of the science of pedagogy deals with the process of thinking in the conditions of mental phenomena, human thinking and the problems of his consciousness. In essence, we often talk about the interaction of the components of perception and reproduction, listening and speaking, receiving and transmitting information with the help of technology. This is undoubtedly the highest standard of knowing the surrounding reality and the linguistic image of the world through the studied language.

Therefore, the cognitive approach to the study of the cognitive process led to the differentiation of cognitive psychology into an independent field of knowledge, which determined its basis by identifying the images of objects in the external world that play a major role in the intellectual development of a person. Thus, in the case of connecting the example of the formation of cognitive competence of students of general education institutions in English using innovative technologies with cognitive psychology, cognitive psychology is "how a person receives information about the world, how it appears to a person, how it is remembered stored and turned into knowledge, how does this knowledge affect human behavior?! learns under his thoughts.

REFERENCES

1. Jalilova D.U. Psychological And Technological Features of Increasing the Efficiency of Educational Activity of Talented Students in Presidential Schools. Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices ISSN NO: 2770-2367 (<https://zienjournals.com>).
2. Лутфуллоев М. Современная дидактика / М. Лутфуллоев [Текст]. - Душанбе, 2010. - 347 с.
3. Madinakhon Alimova Iskandar qizi, Egamberdiev N.B. THE IMPORTANCE OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN DEVELOPING DESIGN ABILITY IN PRESCHOOL AND PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 4 APRIL 2023. 566-569p.
4. Madinakhon Alimova Iskandar qizi, Egamberdiev N.B. WOMEN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN: OPPORTUNITIES AND PROSPECTS. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 4 APRIL 2023. 451-452-453p.
5. Новые педагогические и информационные технологии в системе образования / Е.С. Полат [Текст]. – М.: Педагогика, 2009. – 127 с.
6. Полежаева М.С. Педагогические условия формирования готовности студентов - будущих учителей к работе в поликультурном образовательном пространстве / М.С. Полежаева [Текст]: дисс. ... канд. пед. наук. – Владикавказ, 2015. – 174 с.
7. Сундуков Л.В. Основные тенденции развития профессиональной ориентации в школах Англии: дисс. ... канд. пед. наук. - Минск, 1975. - 205 с.